

ESMA

A Brief Introduction to Basic Concepts of Machine Learning for Psychologists

As my master thesis is written in a psychological department, this electronic supplementary material provides a brief introduction to some fundamental concepts of machine learning, “the systematic study of algorithms and systems that improve their knowledge or performance with experience.” (Flach, 2012, p. 3). It is further described as being “concerned with using the right features to build the right models that achieve the right tasks” (Flach, 2012, p. 12).

Representation of Objects / Data

The input space X consists of all possible objects i , e.g. individual participants. Each object $i \in X$ is typically represented by an n -dimensional feature vector $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_{1,i}, x_{2,i}, \dots, x_{n,i})^{(T)} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ where every dimension corresponds to a measured attribute, for example age, heart rate, personality traits, behavioural data. The space constituted by all possible feature vectors is called feature space $\mathbf{x}_i \in F \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ (e.g., Flach, 2012), each object can also be interpreted as a point in the feature space (e.g., Statnikov et al., 2011).

Geometrical Considerations

As every object i is represented by an n -dimensional feature vector $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$, every object can also be interpreted as a point in the n -dimensional vector space (e.g., Statnikov et al., 2011).

A hyperplane $H \in \mathbb{R}^n$ can be defined by a normal vector $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \mathbf{w} \perp H$ and an arbitrary point $\mathbf{x}_0 \in H$ so that for all points $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ on the hyperplane the dot product $\langle \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0 \rangle = \langle \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{x} \rangle + b$ equals 0 (Ansorge et al., 2010). In addition, for all objects on one

side of the hyperplane the term $\langle \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{x}_i \rangle + b$ will be positive and for all objects on the other side it will be negative so the simple function $\text{Sign}(\langle \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{x}_i \rangle + b)$ can be used as a classifier.

Training a Model

A machine learning algorithm uses data to create a model. This is often referred to as model *training*. In the case of classification, the trained model can be used to assign an output to given input data. To achieve this, the modelling algorithm fits a function \hat{f} that maps feature vectors to an output space: $\hat{f}: X \rightarrow Y, \hat{y} = \hat{f}(\mathbf{x})$ with \hat{f} being an estimate of the true underlying function $f: X \rightarrow Y, y = f(\mathbf{x})$ (e.g., Flach, 2012). The trained model \hat{f} can be used to predict class membership for previously unseen objects.

The training of a predictive function \hat{f} is called supervised learning which requires *labelled training* or *analysis data*: a dataset containing feature vectors as well as their corresponding class membership (e.g., Barua et al., 2024). In psychological research, the outcome is often referred to as the *dependent variable*. The features used as input in a predictive function are often referred to as predictors which are similar to *independent variables*.

The training of a model is based on analysis data, but the goal is to build a model and therefore a classification function $\hat{y} = \hat{f}(\mathbf{x})$ which has good results for previously unseen, new data (Statnikov et al., 2011). This concept is called generalisation – the identified patterns from the analysis data are generalised to all possible data. It “is probably the most fundamental concept in machine learning.” (Flach 2012, p. 6). To examine the model’s generalisation it can be tested with labelled *test* or *assessment data* (\mathbf{x}_i, y_i) which were not used for model training.

Model Performance

In the classical statistics framework, the p -value is often used as the critical criterion to determine whether the relationship between independent and dependent variables is statistically *significant*: $p < .05$ is usually considered to be significant by convention, while $p > .05$ is not. This black-and-white decision is problematic, as already Fisher emphasised: “no scientific worker has a fixed level of significance from year to year, and in all circumstances, he rejects hypothesis; he rather gives his mind to each particular case in the light of his evidence of ideas.” (Fisher, 1956, as cited in Yu, 2022, p. 41). In addition, for very large numbers of observation even a small difference between groups can lead to statistical significance – although the practical and theoretical implications of these results might be questionable. This phenomenon is called *overpowered* sampling or study (Field, 2018). Due to this, the p -value is not sufficient to determine if a model is good (Yu, 2022). Instead, for the assessment of the model performance various metrics are available (e.g., Flach, 2012; Runkler, 2015). They are often based on the ratio of true and false prediction of the assessment data. For binary classification, the 2 x 2 combinations of the actual and the predicted value are shown as *confusion matrix* in Table 1.

Table 1

Confusion Matrix

	Predicted positive	Predicted negative	Row sum
Actual positive	True positive (TP)	False negative (FN)	TP + FN
Actual negative	False positive (FP)	True negative (TN)	FP + TN
Column sum	TP + FP	FN + TN	N

The *accuracy* or proportion of correct classifications is calculated as $(TP + TN) / N$ (e.g., Statnikov et al., 2013) but is sensitive to prior class probabilities. If the overall accuracy

is not relevant but the detection rate of *true* cases (e.g., suicidal patients), *sensitivity* or *recall* provides a better metric: $\text{recall} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FN})$. For the detection of negative cases, a similar metric is *specificity* = $\text{TN} / (\text{TN} + \text{FP})$. To compensate for unbalanced class distribution, metrics like Cohen's Kappa (Cohen, 1960) are available.

In addition, sensitivity and specificity can be used to plot the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve and to calculate the area under the (this) curve (AUC; e.g., Runkler, 2015). This metric shows the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity, as a high sensitivity usually leads to a low specificity and vice versa.

The choice of an appropriate metric depends on the specific task or modelling goal. When different models are to be compared, it is recommended to consider several metrics (Yu, 2022)

Overfitting and the Bias-Variance Dilemma

During model training, the error on the training error is minimised. Unfortunately, on new data the model performance is lower than on the training data: The test error is bigger than the training error (Runkler, 2015). This is a general phenomenon. However, the training error converges to the test error when the number of model parameters is much smaller than the number of observations (Runkler, 2015).

In contrast, *overfitting* occurs when the model reproduces the training data and their underlying pattern too well; resulting in poor performance on new data (Kuhn & Silge, 2022). Therefore, overfitting leads to poor generalisation. This is especially problematic for highly complex models which can almost perfectly fit the noisy training data but show high misclassification rates for unseen data due to the incorporated noise (Flach; Hamel, 2009).

This is sometimes called the bias-variance dilemma: a low-complexity model suffers less from variability due to random variations in the training data, but may introduce a

systematic bias that even large amounts of training data can't resolve; on the other hand, a high-complexity model eliminates such bias but can suffer non-systematic errors due to variance. (Flach, 2012, p. 93)

Therefore, to achieve a good generalisation, the optimal model complexity has to be identified (Runkler, 2015). In general, “a rule of thumb is that, to avoid overfitting, the number of parameters estimated from the data must be considerably less than the number of data points.” (Flach, 2012, p. 93).

Dimensionality Reduction

In general, not all available features are relevant. As it is a basic principle in science, that simpler explanations are preferred (e.g., Field, 2018), models should focus on a small predictor. This serves various purposes: High complex data foster overfitting, high computational cost and data sparsity while dimensionality reduction enhances model interpretation and can reduce noise and therefore improve the model performance (Barua et al., 2024). Common techniques of dimensionality reduction are feature selection and feature extraction by PCA, EFA or – if underlying structures are known previously – SEM (Kuhn & Silge, 2022; Barua et al, 2024).

Feature selection is an important step. From a modelling perspective, selecting the smallest necessary subset for accurate prediction is a problem in itself (Statnikov et al., 2011). If possible, it results from a theory driven way backed by domain knowledge (e.g., Field, 2018). Even though various algorithms are available to find a sufficient predictor set, there is no analytical method to determine the optimal predictor set a priori efficiently. Instead, all possible models would need to be calculated. This all-subset method compares all possible combinations of predictors. Unfortunately, its computing time increases exponentially with the number of predictors as the number of possible subsets is 2^n , it is only suitable for small

predictor set. In general, feature selection methods are grouped into *filter*, *wrapper* and *embedded methods*.

Filter methods are model-invariant, robust and extensive to computation algorithms based on the correlation between features (Sowmyayani, 2022). They remove non-relevant as well as redundant features but do not consider model specific selection criteria. Examples are information gain, chi-square test or correlation coefficient. Interaction terms can also be relevant (Flach, 2012). Unfortunately, filter methods typically do not take them into account.

Wrapper methods evaluate several models with different subsets which are scored by their test errors so that the best feature set can be chosen. These methods' computational effort increases with the number of variables while the overfitting risk increases with insufficient number of observation. Examples are sequential feature selection, recursive feature elimination as well as genetic algorithms (Sowmyayani, 2022). Stepwise approaches (forwards selection, backward elimination etc.), which are also widely known in classical regression methods (e.g., Field, 2018), find for a given model the optimal predictor to add (forward selection) or to remove (backward elimination). Afterwards a new model is calculated and the predictors are examined again. Regarding to Yu (2022), stepwise methods are prone to collinearity within the data and highly sensitive to even small changes in data. In addition, every step is only a step towards a local optimum which does not guarantee to reach the global optimum (Thompson, 1995). Stepwise algorithms benefit from a sensible preselection and preprocessing of features:

Many Big-Data researchers believe that, the larger the number of possible explanatory variables, the more useful is stepwise regression for selecting explanatory variables.

The reality is that stepwise regression is less effective the larger the number of potential explanatory variables. Stepwise regression does not solve the Big-Data

problem of too many explanatory variables. Big Data exacerbates the failings of stepwise regression (Smith, 2018, p. 1).

However, if a stepwise algorithm is used, Field (2018) recommends backward elimination to avoid suppressor effects which are more likely to be encountered with forward selection.

Embedded methods combine wrapper and filter methods. According to Sowmyayani (2022), the most popular embedded method is *LASSO* (least absolute shrinkage and selection operator; Tibshirani, 1996). In addition to standard regression, *LASSO* minimises the absolute sum of the coefficients of the regression term so that the coefficients of unimportant predictors are shrunk towards zero. Unfortunately, when applied to a group of multicollinear features, it tends to remove all but one. *Ridge regression* (Hoerl & Kennard, 1970), which minimises the sum of squared coefficients instead of their absolute sum, does not select features as it does not set coefficients to zero. However, combined with *LASSO* it forms the *elastic net* method (Zou & Hastie, 2005), which overcomes disadvantages of both algorithms: It is capable of selecting features while retaining several of multicollinear features.

Model Selection

The goal of model selection is to determine a model which is suitable for given data (Statnikov et al., 2011) and a given task like classification (e.g., Flach, 2012).

It is a basic principle in science, that simpler explanations are preferred (e.g., Field, 2018) so models should only include as many predictors as necessary. The often quoted Occam's razor favours a simple model over an equally performing but more complex model, should also be considered (Flach, 2012). A common recommendation in literature is to consider a balance between model complexity and model performance when selecting the final model.

It is important to note that even in the paradigm of distinct analysis and assessment data the risk remains that a model fits the assessment data by chance. Thus given, the process of model selection should not be pushed too hard since this would increase the probability of such a one-hit wonder (e.g., Statnikov et al., 2011).

In addition, since in the explorative setting it is often not possible to find the *true* model instead a minimal class of models could be provided for further examination or use by researchers (Nevo & Ritov, 2017; Tsai, 2022).

Recommended resources for Modelling (in R)

To get started in R, *R for Data Science* (Wickham et al., 2023) delivers what the title promises: an introduction to R and the tidyverse. It covers basic operations, data transformation and visualisation, and includes exercises for practice.

Once basic R knowledge is acquired, *Tidy Modeling with R. A Framework for Modeling in the Tidyverse* (Kuhn & Silge, 2022) guides through the whole modelling process with the R package *tidymodels*, while also providing general insights into modelling.

After a model is generated, one might want to understand it. *Interpretable Machine Learning* (Molnar, 2025) offers a broad introduction to model interpretation and presents appropriate methods.

The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference and Prediction (2nd ed.; Hastie et al., 2009) delves deeper into the mathematical and statistical foundations of machine learning, providing fundamental background knowledge and presenting several machine learning algorithms.

References Appendix

- Barua, T., Hiran, K., Jain, R. & Doshi, R. (2024). *Machine Learning with Python*. De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110697186>
- Cohen, J. (1960). A coefficient of agreement for nominal scales. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 20(1).<https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164460020001>
- Field, A. (2018). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS Statistics* (5th ed.). Sage.
- Flach, P. (2012). *Machine learning. The art and science of algorithms that make sense of data*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hamel, L. (2009). *Knowledge Discovery with Support Vector Machines*. Wiley.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470503065>
- Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R., & Friedman, J. (2009) *The elements of statistical learning: Data mining, inference and prediction* (2nd ed.). Springer.<https://hastie.su.domains/ElemStatLearn/>
- Hoerl, A. E., & Kennard, R. W. (1970). Ridge regression: biased estimation for nonorthogonal problems. *Technometrics*, 12(1), 55–67.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00401706.1970.10488634>
- Kuhn, M., & Silge, J. (2022). *Tidy modeling with R. A framework for modeling in the tidyverse*. O'Reilly. <https://www.tmwr.org/>
- Molnar, C. (2025). *Interpretable Machine Learning: A Guide for Making Black Box Models Explainable* (3rd ed.). <https://christophm.github.io/interpretable-ml-book/cite.html>
christophm.github.io/interpretable-ml-book/
- Nevo, D., & Ritov, Y., (2017). Identifying a minimal class of models for high-dimensional data. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 18(24), 1–29.

- Runkler, T. A. (2015). *Data Mining. Modelle und Algorithmen intelligenter Datenanalyse* (2nd ed.). Springer Vieweg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-8348-2171-3>
- Smith, G. (2018). Step away from stepwise. *Journal of Big Data*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-018-0143-6>
- Sowmyayani, S. (2022). Machine Learning. In A. Kumar, S. Sagar, T. Ganesh Kumar, & K. Sampath Kumar (Eds.), *Prediction and analysis for knowledge representation and machine learning* (pp. 1–31). CRC Press.
- Statnikov, A., Aliferis, C. F., Hardin, D. P., & Guyon, I. (2011). *A gentle introduction to support vector machines in biomedicine: Volume 1: Theory and methods*. World Scientific. <https://doi.org/10.1142/7922>
- Thompson, B. (1995). Stepwise regression and stepwise discriminant analysis need not apply here: A guidelines editorial. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 55(4), 525–534. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164495055004001>
- Tibshirani, R. (1996). Regression shrinkage and selection via the lasso. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological)*, 58(1), 267–288, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2517-6161.1996.tb02080.x>
- Tsai, K.-T. (2022). *Machine learning for knowledge discovery with R. Methodologies for modeling, inference and prediction*. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003205685>
- Wickham, H., Çetinkaya-Rundel, M., & Grolemund, G. (2023). *R for Data Science* (2nd ed.). O'Reilly. <https://r4ds.hadley.nz/>
- Yu, C. H. A. (2022). *Data mining and exploration: From traditional statistics to modern data science*. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003153658>

Zou, H., & Hastie, T. (2005). Regularization and variable selection via the elastic net. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*, 67(2), 301–320.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9868.2005.00503.x>